

**THE LEVEL OF UNDERSTANDING AND COMPLIANCE OF SCHOOL OFFICIALS
ON CAMPUS JOURNALISM PROGRAM OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS
IN THE DISTRICT OF BUENAVISTA I, DIVISION OF QUEZON:
BASIS FOR MANAGEMENT IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES**

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ABSTRACT

This study is intended to determine the level of understanding and compliance of school officials on campus journalism program of public elementary schools in the district of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism, student publication, school paper adviser, and press conferences/trainings/seminars. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. The data were statistically analyzed using percentage, frequency, mean, and ranking. The significant relationship between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program was statistically analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson's r). The study has a total of 53 respondents: (1) public school district supervisor, 11 school heads, and 41 school paper advisers who answered the multiple-choice test and questionnaire. Findings revealed that in the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism programs, they highly understood the indicators, with an overall mean frequency of correct answers of 33.52 and a percentage of 75.85. When it comes to compliance, it was found that the four (4) indicators were all moderately complied. Furthermore, the correlation analysis between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials revealed that there is no significant relationship, and the null hypothesis is accepted. Lastly, the proposed implementation strategies for the campus journalism program cater all the least understood and least complied indicators regarding the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the said program.

INTRODUCTION

Campus journalism has been practiced in schools for decades, and it has had a tremendous impact on students' lives. Campus publications are considered essential since they have a big impact on students' opinions, behavior, and political status—especially in light of the shifting social landscape (Asperga, 2017). Journalism, in the opinion of Harcup (2015), fills in the gaps in society's knowledge by defining public interest and educating the public about itself. Campus journalists are empowered by RA 7079 to defend press freedom at the academic level while simultaneously growing as individuals and fostering moral development, critical thinking, and self-discipline (Destacamento, 2012). Campus Journalism Act of 1991 focuses on oral and written communication skills coupled with the principles of truth, fairness, and patriotism. Campus journalism is an integral key in nation- building. The campus press is the concrete manifestation of the students' democratic rights and a tangible expression of press freedom. Some well-known and noteworthy people in Philippine politics, media, art, and literature that have made substantial contributions to their respective disciplines in one way, or another were brought to light by the university press. The campus press instilled in many of them the higher for truth and social change that was the first stirring of their nationalist consciousness (Senate S. No. 1204).

The Buenavista I, one of the well-known districts to compete in Division Schools Press Conferences and Regional Schools Press Conferences has already lost its spotlight. The researcher, who is serving as school paper adviser of Buenavista I, expressed concern on the understanding and compliance of the schools in the implementation of campus journalism program. The inactive status of Buenavista I in school publication, schools should make an emphasis on the implementation of campus journalism program. Some schools comply to the said program but lack of understanding and compliance. The researcher believes that to have an operative campus journalism program, there should be a strong connection between understanding and compliance with campus journalism program. Hence, this study determined the level of understanding and compliance of school officials (school heads, school paper advisers, and public schools district supervisor) on campus journalism program of public elementary schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon. The findings of this study were used as a basis to introduce management implementation strategies on campus journalism program.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of understanding and compliance on campus journalism program of school officials of public elementary schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon as basis for management implementation strategies.

Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of understanding on campus journalism program of school officials of public elementary schools in terms of:
 - 1.1. DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism;
 - 1.2. Student Publication;
 - 1.3. School Paper Adviser;
 - 1.4. Student Publication Funds; and
 - 1.5. Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars?
2. What is the level of compliance on campus journalism program of school officials of public elementary schools in terms of:
 - 1.1. DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism;
 - 1.2. Student Publication;
 - 1.3. School Paper Adviser;
 - 1.4. Student Publication Funds; and
 - 1.5. Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials of selected public elementary schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what management implementation strategies may be developed?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlational research design to determine the correlation between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program of public elementary schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon. Descriptive-correlational research design is used in research studies that aim to present still images of scenarios and demonstrate how certain variables relate to one another (McBurney and White, 2009). This design is appropriate for the study since the goal is to determine how participant variables can influence one another.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon. The District of Buenavista I is composed of 11 public elementary schools, namely: Bagong Silang Elementary School, Buenavista Central Elementary School, Batabat Elementary School, Cabong Elementary School, Dela Paz Elementary School, Del Rosario Elementary School, Mabutag Elementary School, Magallanes Elementary School, Sabang Elementary School, San Isidro Elementary School, and San Vicente Elementary School. The District of Buenavista I is headed by the public schools district supervisor and 11 school heads. There are 133 public elementary school teachers in total as of writing this study. This location was chosen in order to gauge school officials' understanding and compliance with the campus journalism program and, subsequently, to carry out management implementation strategies throughout the district's public primary schools.

Population and Sampling

A total of 53 respondents, (one (1) public schools district supervisor, 11 school heads, and 41 school paper advisers) were the respondents in this study, as shown in Table 1.

These public schools district supervisor, school heads, and school paper advisers were taken from the public elementary schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon.

Respondents	Frequency
I. Public Schools District Supervisor of the District of Buenavista 1	1
II. School Heads of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista 1	
Bagong Silang Elementary School	1
Buenavista Central Elementary School	1
Batabat Elementary School	1
Cabong Elementary School	1
Dela Paz Elementary School	1
Del Rosario Elementary School	1
Mabutag Elementary School	1
Magallanes Elementary School	1
Sabang Elementary School	1
San Isidro Elementary School	1
San Vicente Elementary School	1
III. School Paper Advisers of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista 1	
Bagong Silang Elementary School	7
Buenavista Central Elementary School	7

Batabat Elementary School	3
Cabong Elementary School	3
Dela Paz Elementary School	3
Del Rosario Elementary School	3
Mabutag Elementary School	3
Magallanes Elementary School	3
Sabang Elementary School	3
San Isidro Elementary School	3
San Vicente Elementary School	3
Total	53

Research Instrument

The researcher used a researcher-made questionnaire and test as data gathering tools for the study. The two parts of the instrument are the following: (1) level of understanding on campus journalism of school officials and (2) level of compliance on campus journalism of school officials. The researcher will use a test to measure the level of understanding and questionnaire for compliance of schools district supervisor, school heads, and school paper advisers in the campus journalism program. The test is consisted of 25 items, and the questionnaire is consisted of 50 items. These are the parts of the test and questionnaire (Part 1: DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism, Part 2: Student Publication, Part 3: School Paper Advisers, Part 4: School Publication Funds, and Part 5: Press Conferences, Trainings, and Seminars). The researcher used the following scales in the test and questionnaire as shown in the tables below.

Frequency	Percentage	Verbal Interpretation
45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

The researcher used the measurement scales above to interpret the numerical scores of the respondents in the given test.

Scale	Weigh Assigned	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Very Highly Complied
4	3.50-4.49	Highly Complied
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Complied
2	1.50-2.49	Less Complied
1	1.00-1.49	Not Complied

The researcher used the measurement scales above to interpret the numerical scores of the respondents in the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedures

The instrument underwent validation to ensure that the test and questionnaire contained statements and questions that truly measure the issues of importance in the study. In this regard, the researcher asked for validation from her school head and research adviser. The researcher-made questionnaire also underwent face validation, which included the comments, suggestions, and approvals of the school head, district campus publication coordinator, and school paper adviser from the university.

Final copies of the test and questionnaire were distributed to the respondents after the pilot testing. To ensure that the research instrument was given to the target respondents of the study, the researcher personally distributed test and questionnaire. The respondents were reminded that participating in the study is voluntary, and withdrawal from the study on any grounds will be allowed. Five days were given to the respondents to finalize their responses.

After the given time for the respondents to finalize their responses, the researcher ensured that the test and questionnaire were retrieved. The responses of the participants were confidential, test and questionnaire, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the information gathered from the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher used percentage, frequency, ranking, mean, and Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson's r) as statistical tools in analyzing the gathered data in this study.

The statements in the multiple-choice test were analyzed using frequency and ranking, while the questionnaire was analyzed using mean and ranking.

The consolidated result of the multiple-choice test on the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism was statistically treated using the average frequency of correct answers, the average frequency of percentages, and verbally interpreted. Lastly, the significant relationship between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with campus journalism was analyzed using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r).

RESULTS

Part 1. The Level of Understanding on Campus Journalism Program of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

Table 1. *The Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism*

Statements	Frequency of Correct Answers	Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Best description of campus journalism.	7	13.2	Misunderstood	5
2. Offered trainings of DepEd on campus journalism.	49	92.5	Very Highly Understood	1
3. Main objective of campus journalism.	32	60.4	Moderately Understood	4
4. Memorandum that aims to promulgate the rules and regulations necessary for the effective implementation of RA 7079 otherwise known as the "Campus Journalism Act of 1991".	36	67.9	Highly Understood	3
5. Effects of the new normal education in the role of campus journalism.	42	79.2	Highly Understood	2
OVERALL MEAN	33.2	62.64	Highly Understood	

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 1 presents the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism. It shows the overall mean frequency of correct answers, which is 33.2 with a percentage of 62.64, and is verbally interpreted as highly understood. The majority of respondents got the correct answer in statement 2, which has a frequency of 49 and a percentage of 92.5. On the other hand, the respondents' lowest score and ranking 5th reflect statement 1, which has a frequency of 7 and a percentage of 13.2.

It can be seen from the table that the respondents very highly understood the offer trainings of DepEd on campus journalism which include the district, division, regional, and national schools press conferences. However, the respondents were somehow confused

with the accurate meaning of campus journalism which is to enable campus journalists to exercise their press freedom. T

The notion above is contrary to the study of Estella (2015), in which it was asserted that most of the teachers who act as school paper advisers lack preparedness. The study proved that most of the teachers are not qualified to act as advisers due to a lack of knowledge about journalism. Teachers assigned to handle journalism are clearly under-skilled. Estella’s study found that “the primary factors for the current state of teachers are a lack of formal training, as journalism is not incorporated into the basic education curriculum.”.

Table 2. *The Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Student Publication*

Statements	Frequency of Correct Answers	Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
6. Publishing of student publication.	36	66.0	Highly Understood	3.5
7. Meaning of student publication.	18	34.0	Less Understood	5
8. Relevance of school publication.	36	66.0	Highly Moderately Understood	3.5
9. Best time to publish a school publication.	47	88.7	Very Highly Understood	2
10. Responsible in editing all articles preparatory to submission to the adviser for final editing and approval for publication.	48	90.6	Very Highly Understood	1
OVERALL MEAN	37	69.06	Highly Understood	

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 2 presents the level of understanding of school officials about the campus journalism program in terms of student publication. It shows the overall mean frequency of correct answers, which is 37 with a percentage of 69.06 and is verbally interpreted as highly understood. The respondents answered statement 10 correctly with a frequency of 48 and a percentage of 90.6 and ranked first. Statement 7 has the lowest frequency of 18 with a percentage of 34.0 and is ranked 5th. Meanwhile, statements 6 and 8 were ranked 3rd; they have the same frequency of 36 with a percentage of 66.0.

In the published blog of Yellowbrick (2023), it emphasized the essential duties of the editor-in-chief in campus journalism. It is said that the editor-in-chief is the highest-ranking editorial position within a news organization, responsible for overseeing the entire editorial process, ensuring the quality and integrity of the content, and shaping the overall direction of the publication.

The result shows that the respondent highly understood the indicator. They understood that school publications serve as 'boundary objects' which can potentially help teachers achieve and develop their professionalism by disseminating individual knowledge into the public knowledge domain with transformative learning. Students serve as a watchdog to uncover problems at the respective institution.

Table 3. *The Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of School Paper Adviser*

Statements	Frequency of Correct Answers	Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
11. Process in selecting school paper adviser.	47	88.7	Highly Understood	2
12. Functions of school paper adviser.	38	71.7	Highly Understood	3
13. Difficult role of school paper adviser.	48	90.6	Very Highly Understood	1
14. School paper advisers need to make sure in writing articles for school publication.	32	60.4	Moderately Understood	4
15. Impact of journalistic competence of the school paper advisers on the overall success of the school publication.	31	58.5	Moderately Understood	5
OVERALL MEAN	39.2	73.98	Highly Understood	

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 3 presents the level of understanding of school officials on the campus journalism program in terms of the school paper adviser. It shows the overall mean frequency of correct answers, which is 39.02 with a percentage of 73.98, and is verbally interpreted as highly understood. Statement 13 is ranked first; it has a frequency of 48

and a percentage of 88.7. Statement 5 is ranked 5th with a frequency of 31 and a percentage of 58.5.

In the study conducted by Hester, Bridges, and Rollins (2020), when teachers are stressed and overworked, they may struggle to maintain their focus and motivation. This can negatively impact their efficiency and their ability to provide quality education to their students.

Furthermore, a high workload can also lead to teacher burnout, which can have long-term effects on their health and well-being. When teachers are burned out, they may become disengaged from their work, leading to lower levels of job satisfaction and increased turnover (Mullen, Backer, Chae, & Li, 2020).

The studies above are connected to the result of the table because they point out that teachers who have a heavy workload can affect their teaching performance. This also applies to the role of school paper adviser; their duties and responsibilities may be affected by a heavy workload, which can lead to poor management of school publications and the coaching of student journalists.

Table 4. *The Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Student Publication Funds*

Statements	Frequency of Correct Answers	Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
16. School publication source of funds.	6	11.3	Highly Understood	5
17. Responsible in preparing the budget of school publication.	39	73.6	Highly Understood	1
18. Things to remember about collecting the publication fee.	26	49.1	Very Highly Understood	3.5
19. Inclusion of student publication funds.	32	60.4	Moderately Understood	2
20. Monitoring of financial report of campus journalism expenses.	26	49.1	Moderately Understood	3.5
OVERALL MEAN	25.8	48.7	Highly Understood	

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 4 presents the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of student publication funds. It shows the overall mean frequency of correct answers, which is 25.8 with a percentage of 48.7. The majority of respondents got the correct answer in statement 17 with a frequency of 39 and a percentage of 73.6. Statement 16 is ranked 5th with a frequency of 6 and a percentage of 11.3. Meanwhile, statements 18 and 20 were ranked 3rd with a frequency of 26 and a percentage of 49.1.

According to RA 7079 Section 4, which is relevant to the table's outcome, a student publication is produced by the student body via an editorial board and publication staff made up of students chosen through open and competitive tests. After the journal is founded, its editorial board will independently decide on its editorial stance and oversee its financial operations.

In every school's project and program implementation, source of fund is always considered as hindrance. Likewise, in campus journalism program implementation, problems regarding with school publication funding can't be deny. Though it is important to have a school publication, the school still need to look for ways on how to maximize the source of funds for campus journalism program.

Table 5. *The Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars*

Statements	Frequency of Correct Answers	Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
21. Main objective of the press conferences on campus journalism.	40	75.5	Highly Understood	1.5
22. Highest level of competition in campus journalism.	40	75.5	Highly Understood	1.5
23. People allowed to attend the trainings and seminars on campus journalism.	39	73.6	Highly Understood	3
24. Source of funds for trainings and seminars.	20	37.7	Less Understood	4
25. Common topics on campus journalism seminars.	24	45.3	Moderately Understood	5
OVERALL MEAN	32.6	61.52	Highly Understood	

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 5 presents the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of press conferences, trainings, and seminars. It shows the overall mean frequency of correct answers, which is 32.6 with a percentage of 61.52, and is verbally interpreted as highly understood. Statements 21 and 22 got the same frequency of 40 and percentage of 75.5, both ranked first. On the other hand, statement 25 ranked 5th with a frequency of 24 and a percentage of 45.3.

Press conferences/trainings/seminars on campus journalism mainly focus on the implementation of campus journalism programs, whether they are at the district, division, regional, or national level. Based on the results of the table, school paper advisers were aware that attending press conferences, trainings, and seminars together with student journalists will enhance their knowledge not only in the implementation of the program but also their journalistic writing skills.

However, in the study conducted by Cabaniza (2023), she revealed that budget is not enough in terms of attendance at seminars and trainings; administration determines the budget; there is no budget hearing conducted; there is a lack of scholarship grants; there is a lack of training and seminars for the improvement of writing skills; and there is a lack of attendance at budget management seminars and workshops

Likewise, Cervantes (2017) noted that because of the dearth of funds, pupil-journalists and even their advisers struggle to financially support their participation in activities such as trainings, workshops, and seminars.

Table 6. *The Consolidated Result the Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program (Multiple-Choice Test)*

Indicators	Average Frequency of Correct Answers	Average Percentage of Correct Answers	Verbal Interpretation
1. DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism	33.02	62.64	Highly Understood
2. Student Publication	37	69.06	Highly Understood
3. School Paper Adviser	39.2	73.98	Highly Understood
4. Student Publication Fund	25.8	48.7	Understood
5. Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars	32.6	61.52	Highly Understood
OVERALL MEAN	33.52	75.85	Highly Understood

Legend:

45-50	81-100%	Very Highly Understood
36-44	61-80%	Highly Understood
23-33	41-60%	Moderately Understood
12-22	21-40%	Less Understood
1-11	1-20%	Misunderstood

Table 6 shows the consolidated result of the level of understanding of school officials about the campus journalism program. It registered an overall mean of average frequency of correct answers, which is 33.52, with an average percentage of correct answers of 75.85, and was verbally interpreted as highly understood.

The result of the table clearly shows that the school officials of the district of Buenavista I are well-equipped with the knowledge and skills of the campus journalism program. This also proves that they can train the campus journalists with the fundamentals of writing journalistic articles. Though it can be observed that the school paper advisers came from elementary schools, they have background in campus journalism and have undergone different trainings, workshops, and seminars that have updated their awareness and understanding of the campus journalism program.

Part 2. The Level of Compliance on Campus Journalism Program of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

Table 7. *The Level of Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The school is obediently complying on the DepEd/Division/Regional/National Memorandum on campus journalism program.	2.51	Moderately Complied	8
2. The school is regularly competing in press conferences offered by DepEd.	2.45	Less Complied	9
3. The school complies to DepEd's implementation of campus journalism program policies.	2.49	Less Complied	10
4. The school complies with the objectives on campus journalism implementation under the RA 7079 (Campus Journalism Act of 1991).	2.68	Moderately Complied	1
5. The school paper adviser of the school attends seminars and training offered by DepEd.	2.55	Moderately Complied	7
6. The school conducts school-based trainings for student journalists.	2.62	Moderately Complied	4
7. The school selects the editorial board based in the provisions of RA 7079 (Campus Journalism Act of 1991).	2.60	Moderately Complied	5

8. The school provides learners opportunities to use the skills learned in campus journalism for their future careers.	2.58	Moderately Complied	6
9. The school recognizes the role of journalism in advocating for social consciousness and environmental awareness.	2.66	Moderately Complied	2.5
10. The school teaches the student journalists to enrich learning experiences through healthy and friendly competitions.	2.66	Moderately Complied	2.5
AVERAGE	2.58	Moderately Complied	

Legend:

4.50-5.00	<i>Very Highly Complied</i>	1.50-2.49	<i>Less Complied</i>
3.50-4.49	<i>Highly Complied</i>	1.00-1.49	<i>Not Complied</i>
2.50-3.49	<i>Moderately Complied</i>		

Table 7 shows the level of compliance of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism. The result from the table revealed that the school officials moderately complied with the DepEd roles in campus journalism, as it registered an average weighted mean of 2.58.

Statements 1 and 4-6 have a verbal interpretation of moderately complied. Meanwhile, statement 2 (The school is regularly competing in press conferences offered by DepEd.) has a weighted mean of 2.45, and statement 3 (The school complies with DepEd’s implementation of campus journalism program policies.) has a weighted mean of 2.49, and they are verbally interpreted as less complied.

Joining or competing regularly in press conferences offered by DepEd enables campus journalists to develop their journalistic writing skills. Likewise, the coaches developed their interpersonal skills by conducting small interactions with other coaches they met during the competition. Further, competitions set a framework for practicing and facilitating a growth mindset (Paguirigan, 2023).

Nonetheless, problems with competing regularly in press conferences offered by DepEd are still a big hindrance to schools, especially given the limited resources and funding of the said activity. This notion is supported by the study of Cervantes (2017), where he revealed that, because of the dearth of funds, pupil-journalists and even their advisers struggle to financially support their participation in activities such as trainings, workshops, and seminars.

Table 8. *The Level of Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Student Publication*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
11. The school has student publication that published by the student body through editorial board.	2.74	Moderately Complied	4.5
12. The school has publication staff composed of students selected by fair and competitive examinations.	2.77	Moderately Complied	3
13. The editorial policies and publication funds were determined once the student publication is published.	2.85	Moderately Complied	1.5
14. The student publication informs students about campus events.	2.85	Moderately Complied	1.5
15. The school practices freedom of the press to deliver relevant information	2.74	Moderately Complied	4.5
16. The school uses the student publication as an avenue for students' self-expression.	2.47	Less Complied	7
17. The school publication serves as an opportunity in harnessing students' talents in creative and literary writing.	2.55	Moderately Complied	6
18. The school publication applies communication arts in journalism.	1.83	Less Complied	10
19. The school publication develops students' journalistic investigation.	2.28	Less Complied	9
20. The student publication provides an avenue for ethical use of thoughts.	2.43	Less Complied	8
AVERAGE	2.55	Moderately Complied	

Legend:

4.50-5.00	<i>Very Highly Complied</i>	1.50-2.49	<i>Less Complied</i>
3.50-4.49	<i>Highly Complied</i>	1.00-1.49	<i>Not Complied</i>
2.50-3.49	<i>Moderately Complied</i>		

Table 8 shows the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of student publication. It also revealed that the school officials also complied with the implementation of student publication, as it registered an average weighted mean of 2.55 and was verbally interpreted as moderately complied.

As seen from the table, the less complied indicators are statement 16 (The school uses the student publication as an avenue for students' self-expression.) with a weighted mean of 2.55, statement 18 (The school publication applies communication arts in journalism.) with a weighted mean of 1.83, statement 19 (The school publication develops students' journalistic investigation.) with a weighted mean of 2.28, and statement 20 (The

student publication provides an avenue for ethical use of thoughts.) with a weighted mean of 2.43. The result from the table shows that the application of communication arts ranked 10th (statement 14). Communication arts are vital in making student publications engaging to audiences. It has a wide scope for designing information as well as the use of multimedia.

Mangompit, Flores, and Jaca (2023) concluded in their study that there were five identified themes that affect the implementation of student publication, such as health-related issues, ICT-related issues, connectivity-related issues, adaptability-related issues, and journalism-related issues.

Also, considering the Knowledge Gap Theory, mass media information in a society increases; those with higher socio-economic status acquire this information faster than those with lower socio-economic status. Since most of the schools in the District of Buenavista have students of low socioeconomic status, they cannot adapt quickly to the new means of communication and the delivery of information in student publications. In this challenge, it can be inferred that the socio-economic status of the student journalists is one of the reasons why they acquire the information slowly since they do not have the resources to access it (Qi, An, Zhang, & Wang, 2020).

Table 9. *The Level of Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of School Paper Adviser*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
21. The school paper advisers of the school are selected by the administration from the list of recommendees submitted by the publication staff.	2.53	Moderately Complied	9.5
22. The school paper advisers of the school know the purpose of a student newspaper which is to deliver fair and unbiased information.	2.53	Moderately Complied	9.5
23. The school paper advisers of the school teach responsible journalism.	2.55	Moderately Complied	8
24. The school paper advisers of the schools provide effective technical assistance to student publication.	2.68	Moderately Complied	3
25. The school paper advisers of the school teach journalistic writing competence on student journalists.	2.64	Complied	5.5
26. The school paper advisers of the school set a journalistically professional	2.58	Moderately Complied	7

learning atmosphere and experience for the students.			
27. The school paper advisers of the school discern and analyze the newsworthy news and issues.	2.64	Moderately Complied	5.5
28. The school paper advisers of the school practice the freedom of the press.	2.66	Moderately Complied	4
29. The school paper advisers of the school serve as the motivator and catalyst for ideas.	2.72	Moderately Complied	2
30. The school paper advisers of the school display special parental authority.	2.85	Moderately Complied	1
AVERAGE	2.67	Moderately Complied	

Legend:

4.50-5.00	<i>Very Highly Complied</i>	1.50-2.49	<i>Less Complied</i>
3.50-4.49	<i>Highly Complied</i>	1.00-1.49	<i>Not Complied</i>
2.50-3.49	<i>Moderately Complied</i>		

Table 9 presents the level of compliance of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of the school paper adviser. The result shows an average weighted mean of 2.67 and is verbally interpreted as moderately complied.

Aside from that, the table shows that all indicators were met by the respondents. Statement 30 (The school paper advisers of the school display special parentals.) with a weighted mean of 2.85 ranked first. Statement 21 (The school paper advisers of the school are selected by the administration from the list of recommendees submitted by the publication staff.) and Statement 22 (The school paper advisers of the school know the purpose of a student newspaper, which is to deliver fair and unbiased information.) have the same weighted mean of 2.53 and rank 9th.

In connection with the result of statement 21, the study of Espadero (2022) revealed in her findings that issues regarding qualifications, relevant training, security, and tenure surfaced in the selection of school paper advisers. As teachers were, from time to time, transferred from one coordinatorship to another, this was supported by the issue of the transfer of accountability from one school head to the next school head, and that reorganization of teaching staff happened as well. This means that some schools qualified a school paper adviser without considering the set of standards in RA 7079.

Additionally, he stated that administrators need to realize that assigning advisers to handle the task undermines the goal of student media and is bad for students' education. Teachers of journalism need to be able to concentrate more on the learners and their process of learning than on the final output.

Table 10. *The Level of Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Student Publication Funds*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
21. The school funding for the student publication includes the savings of the respective school's appropriations.	2.51	Moderately Complied	6
22. The school funding for the student publication includes the student subscriptions.	2.64	Moderately Complied	2
23. The school funding for the student publication includes the donations.	2.70	Moderately Complied	1
24. The editorial board of the school provides mechanism in collecting publication fees from students.	2.60	Moderately Complied	4
25. The school legalizes the non-mandatory collection of public fees for school publication as stated in the Section 7 of the RA 7079 (Campus Journalism Act of 1991).	2.62	Moderately Complied	3
26. The school provides a transparency of funding of student publication.	2.36	Less Complied	8
27. The school budget supports the funding of student publication.	2.28	Less Complied	9
28. The budget of school publication is posted in school's bulletin board.	2.09	Less Complied	10
29. The budget of school publication is prepared year-round.	2.49	Less Complied	7
30. The editorial board of the school manages the budget of school publication.	2.58	Moderately Complied	5
AVERAGE	2.48	Less Complied	

Legend:

4.50-5.00	<i>Very Highly Complied</i>	1.50-2.49	<i>Less Complied</i>
3.50-4.49	<i>Highly Complied</i>	1.00-1.49	<i>Not Complied</i>
2.50-3.49	<i>Moderately Complied</i>		

Table 10 shows the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of student publication funds. The result indicates an average weighted mean of 2.48 and is verbally interpreted as less complied.

Statement 33 was supported by RA 7079 Section 7; it is stated that funding for the student publication shall be sourced primarily from student publication fees collected by the school administration. It shall be mandatory for the school administration to collect reasonable student publication and subscription fees during the enrollment period. For public schools, publication funds shall be included in the budgets of the institutions. Secondary sources of publication funds shall include the savings of the respective school's appropriations and donations.

On the other hand, the table shows statement 10 (The budget of school publication is posted on the school's bulletin board.) is the least complied indicator. In the study of Talikan (2021), it was concluded that if the schools want to improve the quality of

education, then posting the liquidation report on the transparency board is necessary. This also attracts investors, philanthropists, and other stakeholders to extend services to the school.

Table 11. *The Level of Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program in terms of Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars*

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
21. The school trains the student writers to be responsible writers in the exercise of press freedom.	2.75	Moderately Complied	1
22. The school paper advisers of the school give effective and efficient technical assistance for student writers.	2.57	Moderately Complied	8
23. Advancing the school paper advisers and student writers' knowledge about the new trends on campus journalism.	2.64	Moderately Complied	2
24. Attend seminars/press conferences/trainings that upskills the school paper advisers and student writers' journalistic competence.	2.57	Moderately Complied	8
25. The school ensures the student writers to write information that is fair, balanced, and truthful.	2.57	Moderately Complied	8
26. Expenses of school paper advisers and student writers in seminars/trainings/workshops/and press conferences attended is covered by the student publication funds.	2.53	Moderately Complied	10
27. Attend seminars/trainings/workshops/and press conferences that provoke student writers' curiosity.	2.60	Moderately Complied	4.5
28. Attend seminars/trainings/workshops/and press conferences that provoke student writers' communication skills.	2.58	Moderately Complied	6
29. Attend seminars/trainings/workshops/and press conferences that strengthen school paper advisers and student writers' journalistic values.	2.60	Moderately Complied	4.5
30. Attend seminars/trainings/workshops/and press conferences on campus journalism implementation.	2.62	Moderately Complied	3
AVERAGE	2.60	Moderately Complied	

Legend:

4.50-5.00	<i>Very Highly Complied</i>	1.50-2.49	<i>Less Complied</i>
3.50-4.49	<i>Highly Complied</i>	1.00-1.49	<i>Not Complied</i>
2.50-3.49	<i>Moderately Complied</i>		

Table 11 shows the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of press conferences/trainings/seminars. The result revealed an average weighted mean of 2.60 and was verbally interpreted as moderately complied.

Based on the result, all the indicators were met by the respondents. Statement 41 (The school trains the student writers to be responsible writers in the exercise of press freedom.) ranked 1st with a weighted mean of 2.75, and Statement 46 (Expenses of school paper advisers and student writers in seminars, trainings, workshops, and press conferences attended are covered by the student publication funds) ranked 10th with a weighted mean of 2.53. RA 7079 was established for several reasons, one of which is to protect press freedom on college campuses and to encourage the growth of campus journalism as a way to reinforce moral principles, foster critical and creative thinking, and help young Filipinos develop their moral character and self-discipline.

As mentioned in the news written by Caling (2020), one of the interviewees said that the workshops and training for campus journalism were funded by themselves a lot of the time, the school is under budget, and their school paper advisers pay for the remaining balances, which they directly source from their own income.

In addition, in the study of Natividad and Gapasin (2021), it was revealed that there is no budget allotted for press conferences, trainings, or seminars for campus journalists and teachers. SPAs stated that if there are DepEd-offered trainings, only the big schools can attend because they have the budget.

Since the law (RA 7079) mandates no mandatory collection of publication fees, this leaves the schools to rely solely on voluntary contributions, donations, and the school's local funds.

Part 3. The Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Understanding and Compliance of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

Table 12. Correlation Analysis between the Level of Understanding and Compliance of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program

Indicators	R-value	P-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism	-0.02	2.73E-05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Student Publication	0.15	4.54E-07	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Paper Adviser	-0.81	1.43E-09	Accept Ho	Not Significant
School Publication Fund	0.69	3.03E-05	Reject Ho	Significant
Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars	0.58	1.63E-07	Reject Ho	Significant
OVERALL TOTAL	0.236	2.21E-30	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 12 shows the correlation analysis between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials on campus journalism program, with an overall total of an R-value of 0.236 and a P-value of 2.21E-30. It can be gleaned from the data that there is no significant relationship between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. The result implies that the high understanding of school officials on different indicators of the campus journalism program doesn't affect the level of compliance of school officials on different indicators of the campus journalism program, and vice versa. This suggests that there is no linear relationship between the level of understanding and the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program.

Part 4. The Proposed Management Implementation Strategies

The proposed management implementation strategies were based on the findings of the study. All the least understood, misunderstood, least complied, and not complied indicators from statement of the problem 1 and 2 were highlighted. Its primary objectives are to elevate the management implementation strategies of public elementary schools in the district of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon on campus journalism program, to develop instructional skills of school paper advisers in coaching campus journalists, and to address the problems of the schools in understanding and compliance with campus journalism program. The researcher crafted an action plan for the proposed management implementation strategies. The priorities of action, objectives, strategies, actions to be taken, time frame, person/s involved, source of funds, and expected outcomes were the contents of the action plan. Furthermore, the researcher believed that through the research output, the implementation of campus journalism program will have clear direction and set appropriate and achievable objectives.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

The significant findings of the study are summarized below:

1. The Level of Understanding on Campus Journalism Program of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

1.1. The level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism programs in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism shows that the majority of respondents answered statement 2 (Not included in the offer of training for DepEd on campus journalism).

1.2. In terms of student publication, the level of understanding of school officials in the campus journalism program shows that the respondents correctly answered statement 10 (Responsible for editing all articles preparatory for submission to the adviser for final editing and approval for publication).

1.3. The level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of school paper advisers shows that the majority of respondents correctly answered statement 13 (Difficult roles of school paper adviser).

1.4. In terms of student publication, the level of understanding of school officials in the campus journalism program shows that the respondents correctly answered statement 17 (Responsible for preparing the budget for school publication).

1.5. In terms of press conferences/trainings/seminars, the level of understanding of school officials on the campus journalism program showed that most respondents correctly answered statement 21 (Main objective of the press conferences on campus journalism) and 22 (Highest level of competition in campus journalism).

Consolidated Result of the Level of Understanding of School Officials on Campus Journalism Program (Multiple-Choice Test)

The result revealed that the respondents highly understood the campus journalism program and its four (4) indicators (DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism, Student Publication, School Paper Advisers, Student Publication Funds, and Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars).

2. The Level of Compliance on Campus Journalism Program of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

2.1. The school officials moderately complied with the campus journalism program in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism.

2.2. The school officials moderately complied on campus journalism program in terms of student publication.

2.3. The school officials moderately complied on campus journalism program in terms of school paper advisers.

2.4. The school officials lowly complied on campus journalism program in terms of student publication funds.

2.5. The school officials moderately complied on campus journalism program in terms of press conferences, trainings, and seminars.

3. The Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Understanding and Compliance of School Officials of Public Elementary Schools in the District of Buenavista I, Division of Quezon

3.1. The result of the correlation analysis between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the on-campus journalism program shows no significant relationship.

4. The Proposed Management Intervention Strategies

4.1. The proposed management implementation strategies were based on the indicators of multiple-choice test and questionnaire with the least understood and complied indicators.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are presented:

1. Based on the result of the multiple-choice test on the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program, it was found that the indicator DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism got the highest frequency of correct answers.
 2. Based on the result of the survey questionnaire on the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program, it was found that the four (4) indicators (DepEd Roles in Campus Journalism, Student Publication, School Paper Advisers, Student Publication Funds, and Press Conferences/Trainings/Seminars) were all moderately complied except for the Student Publication Funds, wherein it was verbally interpreted as less complied.
 3. Based on the consolidated result of the multiple-choice test on the level of understanding of school officials in the campus journalism program, it was found that the respondent highly understood the indicators.
 4. The result of the correlation analysis between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials revealed that there is no significant relationship between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.
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Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Since the result of the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism programs in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism shows a low frequency of correct answers in statement 1 (Best describes campus journalism), school officials may reconsider RA 7079, (Section 1) and review the meaning of campus journalism.
2. Because the result of the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism programs in terms of student publication shows a low average frequency of correct answers in statement 7 (Meaning of school publication), school officials may also revisit RA 7079, specifically Section 4 of the law where the meaning of school publication was explained.
3. Because the result of the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of school paper adviser shows a low frequency of correct answers in statement 15 (Impact of journalistic competence of school paper advisers on the overall success of the school publication.) school officials may reflect on their performance as school paper advisers and how it affects the success of school publication.

4. Since the result of the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism programs in terms of student publication funds shows a low frequency of correct answers in statement 6 (Source of funds for school publication.) school officials should assess the source of funds for school publication, e.g., savings of the respective school's appropriations, student subscriptions, donations, and other sources of funds.

5. Since the result of the level of understanding of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of press conferences, trainings, and seminars shows a low frequency of correct answers in statement 25 (Common topics on campus journalism seminars.), we may review DepEd memoranda that issued press conferences, trainings, and seminars for school paper advisers and campus journalists and analyze the objectives.

6. Based on the results of the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of DepEd roles in campus journalism, it shows that the schools' compliance with DepEd's implementation of campus journalism program policies is the least complied statement: therefore, the school officials must consider the implementation of RA 7079 since it serves as the mother law of campus journalism.

7. The result of the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of student publication shows that the least complied statement is the application of communication arts in journalism. The school officials may start to integrate the use of multimedia in delivering newsworthy articles.

8. The result of the level of compliance of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of school paper advisers shows that the least complied statement are the selection of school paper advisers and the awareness of the school paper advisers with the purpose of student newspaper which is to deliver fair and unbiased information, the school administrators may refrain from selecting school paper advisers which are solely based on the length of teaching experience and not by their teaching performance specially those teachers with journalism background, and lastly, school paper advisers should always give effective technical assistance to campus journalists to make sure that they publish fair and unbiased information.

9. Since the result of the level of compliance of school officials on campus journalism program in terms of student publication funds shows least compliance in posting of school publication budget in school's bulletin board, school officials should always uphold transparency and accountability, they need to post in school's bulletin board all the expenses and sources of funds for student publication.

10. Because the results of the level of compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program in terms of press conferences, trainings, and seminars show the least compliance with the expenses of school paper advisers and student

writers in seminars, trainings, workshops, and press conferences covered by publication funds, the school may raise funds by being open to donations, maximizing the school's local funds, and funding support from LGU.

11. Since the result of the correlation analysis between the level of understanding and compliance of school officials with the campus journalism program shows no significant relationship, the school officials should align the high level of understanding with how they comply with the different aspects of campus journalism.

12. Since the limitation only concerns the understanding and compliance of school officials on campus journalism program, future researchers may also conduct study about the school paper advisers and campus journalists' journalistic competence. This study may also serve as their reference into further studying the implementation of campus journalism program in public elementary schools.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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